

ITCER Newsletter

Issue No. 2 / Year 2026

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International Training Centre for Environmental Research

Issue Purpose

This issue reports selected developments since the 2025 newsletter. It gives a concise view of recent work at Ng'iya, current capacities, cooperation opportunities, and next steps in biodiversity monitoring, environmental data work, training, and applied environmental research.

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Editorial / Welcome Note

This second issue of the ITCER Newsletter reports recent developments at the Ng'iya site and in the wider ITCER programme. The previous issue, available at [Zenodo](#), introduced ITCER, its site, and its main fields of work. The present issue focuses on progress since then, current capacities, cooperation, and next steps.

At Ng'iya, field observation, laboratory development, and digital data work are closely connected. Biodiversity monitoring provides records for research and training. The developing infrastructure supports applied environmental work and structured data generation.

A central point of this issue is the combined role of ITCER as a training-oriented and research-active institution. Practical training is linked with biodiversity documentation, long-term observation, software work, and the validation of research data.

ITCER works under real local conditions. Climate pressure, infrastructure needs, security questions, and employment prospects for qualified young people all influence planning. The following pages therefore present recent progress and the practical framework for cooperation.

Figure 1: Information and discussion meeting with local farmers and supporters at the ITCER site on May 30, 2026. The programme combined information, exchange, and entertainment. *Credit: ITCER Kenya.*

Recent News

Since the previous newsletter, the main news concerned visits and exchanges, the biodiversity-image archive, environmental IT, and outputs from the Ng'iya grassland experiment.

Student groups from the University of Tübingen visited the Ng'iya site in March 2025 and again in March 2026. Local motorbike riders contributed to the discussion and calibration of the Fair Fare software in May 2025. In October 2025, representatives of the Public Benefit Organizations Regulatory Authority visited the site, while members of the University of Hohenheim joined an online seminar.

Further exchanges involved colleagues associated with NEMA, Siaya Polytechnic, and TNTP, as well as a co-founder of ICIPE, farmers from Siaya County, graduates, and local supporters. A roundtable with Siaya graduates and a PBORA official also explored start-up opportunities in the environmental IT sector.

By early June 2026, the biodiversity monitoring archive contained more than 45,000 images, of which more than 36,000 were already linked to taxon names. The documented records included 2,714 species-level taxa, 559 unresolved genus-level entries, and 182 unresolved family-level entries. Work also continued on the data pathway through Diversity Workbench and the SNSB GBIF Data Publisher in Munich, together with AI-supported identification and dataset management.

The SSRN-listed manuscript *Grassland Management Intensity Drives Ecosystem Productivity and Drought Tolerance Via Plant–Microbe–Soil Feedbacks* represents another recent result. Its first and last authors, Moses M. Ngugi and Michaela A. Dippold, are affiliated with the University of Tübingen. The study draws on the long-term grassland experiment at Ng'iya and the wider grassland-management programme.

ITCER Today: Organisation and Cooperation

ITCER works through two complementary organisations. ITCER Kenya carries the local basis for the Ng'iya site, while ITCER e.V. in Germany supports membership, fundraising, and cooperation with European and other international partners.

During the past years, the Ng'iya site has developed into a practical base for fieldwork, laboratory development, biodiversity monitoring, server infrastructure, training, and cooperation. The long-term grassland experiment, the photographic monitoring programme, the laboratory facilities, and the tree nursery are part of this growing working environment.

New activities are discussed in relation to the work already running at Ng'iya. This includes timing, available staff time, infrastructure use, data handling, authorship, credit, outputs, and follow-up. The aim is to make cooperation clear, useful, and manageable for all participants.

Training for qualified young Kenyans is linked with concrete tasks in field monitoring, biodiversity informatics, GIS, laboratory methods, image documentation, environmental data services, and web tools. In this way, training contributes to practical outputs and documented research data.

Cooperation in Practice

- New activities are discussed early, so that timing and responsibilities are clear.
- Practical arrangements cover the use of infrastructure, materials, data, staff time, authorship, credit, outputs, and local support where needed.
- Activities are coordinated with ongoing work at the Ng'iya site. This includes the grassland experiment, biodiversity monitoring, laboratory work, server use, training, and site maintenance.
- Shared standards help to make cooperation transparent and useful for everyone involved.

Scientific and Data Practice

- ITCER aims to document field observations, images, samples, and related data in a traceable way.
- Important records should include stable identifiers, locality, geocoordinates, date, responsible contributors, and links to images or source material where possible.
- Derived digital objects should remain connected with their source records, processing steps, versions, and responsible contributors.
- These practices help to build a reusable scientific data basis for monitoring, research, training, and cooperation.

Recent Highlights

One important area of progress is the biodiversity image workflow from field recording to structured data export. Smartphone-based field documentation is increasingly linked with image storage, taxonomic revision, AI-supported identification, and preparation for external biodiversity data systems.

The current workflow starts with field images and metadata recorded in the ITCER monitoring system. Records are reviewed, linked to taxon names, checked for consistency, and prepared for export. After post-processing, formatted data can be transferred into the Diversity Workbench / DiversityCollection environment.

This pathway connects the local ITCER database with the SNSB GBIF Data Publisher in Munich. It provides the technical route for later international biodiversity data publication and creates a documented chain from field observation to curated digital record.

Kenyan graduates and ITCER co-workers are involved in image review, taxonomic data handling, metadata checking, export preparation, and workflow testing. These tasks provide practical experience in biodiversity informatics, environmental data management, and software-supported documentation.

Figure 2: Overview of ITCER's structure and activities: funding, work at the site, seminars and workshops, environmental IT, and future opportunities for Kenyan graduates. *Credit: ITCER Kenya.*

Figure 3: Data-flow overview from field documentation and ITCER database processing through Diversity Workbench and DiversityCollection to the SNSB GBIF Data Publisher workflow. *Credit: ITCER Kenya.*

Special Feature: AI Image Pipeline and Environmental Innovation

Author: Brian Ochieng Oloo | International Training Centre for Environmental Research (ITCER)

Figure 4: ITCER Dataset Explorer in the model-training view, with dataset selection, image annotations, COCO bounding boxes, class categories, and preparation of species-image training data. *Credit: ITCER Kenya.*

Across Kenya and East Africa, environmental projects are generating increasing amounts of image data. Camera traps, field surveys, drone images, remote-sensing workflows, and citizen-science contributions can document plants, animals, habitats, land use, and ecological change. These data become most useful when they are transformed into structured records that can be searched, checked, analysed, and shared.

Within the ITCER AI Image Pipeline project, my focus is on helping to turn ecological imagery into structured biodiversity information. The pipeline links field images with species names, confidence scores, geographic coordinates, dates, habitat information, and other metadata. These outputs can support monitoring, distribution analysis, conservation planning, biodiversity databases, and environmental dashboards.

The current technical work includes image upload, annotation, dataset assembly, class and tag management, COCO bounding boxes, versioning, basic analytics, and preparation of training data for AI-supported identification. Field photographs from the Siaya monitoring programme can be reviewed, annotated, and combined into reusable datasets. In this way, image recording, taxonomic revision, data management, and model development become parts of one workflow.

Artificial intelligence can extend expert capacity by supporting routine screening, sorting, and prioritisation. Experts remain central to the process. Uncertain records can be selected for review, corrected results can be added to the dataset, and the quality of the model can improve through repeated validation. This is especially important for long-term monitoring, where thousands

of images accumulate over several years.

The engineering work behind such a system is detailed. Field images often contain changing light conditions, motion blur, vegetation cover, weather effects, complex backgrounds, and partly visible organisms. Reliable results therefore require careful dataset preparation, annotation rules, testing, validation, storage infrastructure, and workflow design. Model selection is one part of the task; the full pipeline from field recording to final data use is equally important.

ITCER provides a strong setting for this work because the image data come from real field activities and real environmental questions. Systems developed here can be adapted to local species, local ecosystems, available infrastructure, and practical conservation needs. This creates an opportunity to build locally useful technology instead of depending mainly on external platforms.

The project also has a training and innovation dimension. Students and young professionals can gain practical experience in artificial intelligence, software engineering, biodiversity informatics, environmental data science, GIS, and web-based data tools. These skills can support research, conservation, education, employment, and later environmental technology initiatives.

My long-term vision is to help connect environmental research, artificial intelligence, and entrepreneurship. Biodiversity data should support scientific work, but they can also become practical tools and services for researchers, conservation organisations, government agencies, educational institutions, and local communities. AI-assisted species identification, biodiversity monitoring tools, ecological data management systems, geospatial applications, and decision-support platforms could all become part of this wider environmental intelligence approach.

Vision

To transform environmental research and biodiversity data into practical AI-driven solutions that strengthen conservation, education, innovation, and sustainable development by converting field imagery into timely, accurate, and actionable biodiversity intelligence for local, regional, and global impact.

Developments and Planned Activities

ITCER will continue work on the biodiversity image archive, including taxonomic revision and selected datasets for international publication. Work will also continue on the Ng'iya grassland plots and the plant nursery.

Further activities are planned in the image workflow and in AI-supported identification. This includes meta-data checking, export routines, server use, GIS, and environmental IT training.

Selected work with young graduates will remain linked

to image documentation, field monitoring, biodiversity informatics, web tools, and environmental data services.

Where results have practical relevance, short technical notes or white papers may be prepared for local partners. ITCER will also explore ground-truthing for satellite observations with colleagues in Cameroon.

New ideas and cooperation offers are welcome when they fit the work at Ng'iya. Practical details will be discussed early.

Support & Join

Donations made through the online donation portal are received by ITCER e.V. in Germany and transferred to ITCER Kenya. They mainly support the local staff basis at Ng'iya. General administration, building work, repairs, and separate project expenses are covered

through other sources or specific agreements.

Membership in ITCER e.V. or ITCER Kenya is also welcome. Questions, membership enquiries, and offers of support may be sent to itcer@gmx.net. Further information is available at <https://itcer.org>.

Closing and Acknowledgements

Figure 5: ITCER staff and co-workers at the Ng'iya site. *Credit: ITCER Kenya.*

ITCER thanks all members, supporters, collaborators, students, visitors, and friends who contributed during the past year.

Particular thanks go to the Public Benefit Organizations Regulatory Authority (PBORA) for its advice and encouragement, and to Equity Bank Siaya for assistance with banking and financial procedures.

Special appreciation is extended to the staff and co-workers at the Ng'iya site. Their daily presence supports training, research, community contacts, field activities, administration, and digital development.

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